

CREATING LEVERAGE TO ENHANCE BIODIVERSITY OUTCOMES
OF GLOBAL BIOMASS TRADE

Value chain modeling at the actor level using **GLOBIOM** Deliverable 6.5

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

One of the objectives of the CLEVER project is to improve and mobilize modelling tools to explore the effectiveness of innovative international trade and supply chain governance interventions on non-food biomass supply chains and biodiversity. This modelling component relies on the GLOBIOM land use model, which projects the dynamics of most important agricultural and forestry supply chains and their impacts on natural resources from the year 2000 into the future with a decadal time step (up to 2050 or even 2100).

As compared to other forward-looking dynamic supply chains modelling tools, this model has a relatively broad and yet detailed modelling of supply chains, covering globally the consumer demand for final products, trade and the supply of products at the scale of 59 market regions and for more than 50 products. The modelling of each agricultural and forestry production activities and related land and water use is done at the subnational scale, with multiple crop, livestock and forestry management intensities and a detailed land cover and land use change representation. A recent extension was allowed to cover blue food supply chains, i.e., fish and seafood. The modelling relies on a large number of datasets from various sources (e.g., ranging from country-level or regional-level price elasticities and official statistics, to high spatial resolution datasets such remote sensing-based land cover products and biophysical model outputs). The standard version of the model balances across several priorities (e.g., high level of detail in modelled variables, use of globally available data products, sufficiently low computation time) and is continuously updated as new datasets and methods become available, and specific modelling goals are pursued.

The model and scenario applications in CLEVER focus on the nexus of trade, supply chain governance and biodiversity impacts for three specific supply chains: soy – with a particular focus on Brazil and the EU, forest biomass – with a specific focus on Brazil and the EU, and aquaculture and aquafeed (globally). In order to improve the underlying GLOBIOM modelling framework for the CLEVER project, a number of activities have been undertaken in Workpackage 6. Deliverable 6.2 reported on initial supply chain modelling improvements (Task 6.2), with explicit integration of the outputs of other tasks in WP6 such as new biophysical modelling outputs (Task 6.1), and improved biodiversity modelling methods and data (Task 6.3).

This deliverable (D 6.5) presents additional model developments that have been undertaken under task 6.5 for each supply chain, with a focus on value chain modeling at the actor level. While it wasn't feasible to introduce novel supply chain actors in the model (e.g., traders, processors, retailers), we focused on selected refinements the modeling of actors already represented in the model (producers, consumers, downstream sectors for forest products). This included topics such as production techniques (e.g., more detailed forest management, use of soy-corn double cropping in Brazil, developments of unfed aquaculture and wild catch for blue food), related public and hybrid regulations (e.g., Brazil's Forest Code and Amazon Soy Moratorium, forestry-related restoration and protection policy in Brazil and the EU), trade related regulations (i.e., EU Deforestation Regulation, EU-MERCOSUR regional trade agreement), alternative future consumption choices (e.g., substitutions between blue food products) and downstream sector material use rate (e.g., recycling and re-use for wood-based products). These improvements have supported in CLEVER WP7 more realistic quantitative

projections (using the GLOBIOM model) of historical trends, and tailored new future scenarios. The latter explored multiple potential future developments for each supply chain, in relation to assumptions about changes at multiple points of value chains, in relation to specific policies and empirical evidence about how specific actors might react (see D7.2 and D7.3).

This deliverable is organized in two main sections. In the INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES, we provide, for each supply chain, a short overview of the key model developments that have been undertaken and of their objectives. Then, in the MODEL DEVELOPMENT section, more details are provided on the status quo in the standard model version, the methods and data sources employed for improving the model, and the different scenarios that leverage the model improvements.

The modelling developments have allowed for significant improvements for each of the three focus supply chains. The latter were also informed by the feedback received from stakeholders during stakeholder workshops for each of the three supply chains as well as written feedback in the case of the soy supply chain. Not all suggestions made by stakeholders are technically feasible and some were beyond the scope of the project (see supply chain-specific sub-sections below), still the value-chain specific knowledge of the stakeholders helped us in prioritizing specific model improvements which then enabled corresponding scenario analyses presented in D7.3.

Soy supply chains

Achievements: several features were introduced in GLOBIOM to improve the representation of supply chain governance initiatives (including both public policies and private sector initiatives) in Brazil and the EU as well as of the soy cropping system in Brazil. These include improving the representation of key land use policies in Brazil (such as the Forest Code and the Amazon Soy Moratorium) in the baseline, as well as the parametrization of alternative scenarios considering either a strengthening or a weakening of these land conservation policies, which was pointed to as relevant by stakeholders. Regarding EU policies, econometric modelling and a literature review have been used to estimate the potential impact of the EU Deforestation Regulation (EUDR) and the EU-Mercosur trade agreement (EUM) on Brazil's exports of soy-based products to the EU, and these estimates have then been parametrized into the GLOBIOM model, including through stakeholder feedback on the plausibility of estimates generated in WP3. To provide insights into alternative policy options in the EU, namely a border biodiversity adjustment mechanism, a footprinting module was developed in GLOBIOM. It estimates the amount of primary product embedded in the supply, processing, trade and final consumption of all agricultural products and regions covered in the model, and associated biodiversity impacts. A finer assessment of key aspects affected future soy demand in China, such as dietary preferences and feed concentrate uptake in monogastric livestock production systems, as suggested by stakeholders, would have required additional resources. Finally, additional developments were undertaken to improve the representation of the soy and soy-corn double cropping systems in Brazil, including their dynamics in terms of area expansion and production volumes at the subnational level.

Forest supply chains

Achievements: several features were introduced in the GLOBIOM-forest model to improve the representation of forest management systems, land use dynamics (incl. future deforestation and afforestation trends), and forest carbon balance, among others. These include refining the representation of forest management by explicitly modeling the dynamics of different age-class cohorts in managed forests (and related carbon stocks) and carbon uptake in plantation forests. Accountings of carbon stored in harvested wood products (WWP) and bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS) systems have also been developed, as well as an accounting of substitution effects between wood-based and fossil fuel-based products and resulting carbon storage. These improvements allow for a more comprehensive analysis of forest carbon balance in scenarios developed in D7.2 and D7.3. Model adjustments were also undertaken to parametrize circular bioeconomy scenarios (i.e., increasing wood recycling and reuse and cascading use of biomass) as well as scenarios looking at the impact of forest protection and land restoration policies in the EU and Brazil on the forest sector, forest carbon balance and biodiversity (see D7.3). This was noted by stakeholders as of particular relevance, but was done in a simple manner, as the input from other parts of the project was able to support detailed work on specific policies. E.g., more tailored work for forestry and restoration in Brazil would have required additional resources (e.g., to bring together developments for soy and forest supply chains) and stakeholder engagement. Finally, to get a better understanding of the socio-economic impacts of different scenarios on the forestry sector in various regions, an indicator of regional competitiveness based on the net trade of all wood products, aggregated in terms of roundwood equivalents, has been developed.

Aquaculture and aquafeed supply chains

Achievements: several improvements were undertaken for the aquaculture and aquafeed supply chains, including improvements to the baseline projections for unfed aquaculture developments as well as the parametrization of new scenarios in the GLOBIOM-fish module. Modifications to the baseline projections include an increase in unfed aquaculture after 2020 following historical developments, which was considered as a more realistic assumption by stakeholders than keeping unfed aquaculture capacity fixed at 2020 levels (as previously considered). An alternative scenario was also developed, examining the impacts of a change in the composition of crop aquafeed in China – as compared to keeping crop aquafeed composition constant over time as in the baseline and in other scenarios. Finally, two new scenarios were also parametrize in the model, examining the impacts of the global adoption of sustainable fisheries management (and associated moderate increase in catch levels after 2020) and of a shift towards more sustainable blue food diets, considering a partial replacement of freshwater fish consumption by mollusks. The consideration of potential future changes in aquaculture sector regulation and of the development of novel, integrated circular aquaculture systems was mentioned as of interest by stakeholders, but would have required literature, data collection and stakeholder engagement beyond available resources.

Differences to previous versions

Version	Date	Differences
Version 1.0	October 8 th 2025	-

Version 2.0	January 23 rd 2026	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- the executive summary was edited to clarify further how suggestions from stakeholders were included- In the soy supply chains subsection of the MODEL DEVELOPMENTS section, a note was added on potential uses of the TRASE data in GLOBIOM, and associated challenges.
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INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES

Soy supply chains

As part of CLEVER WP7, we use the GLOBIOM model to quantitatively assess future scenarios on soy supply chains, designed to explore the impact of both broad world trends (e.g., business-as-usual, global food system transformation towards biodiversity goals, long-term aftermath of US-China trade dispute) and specific international and domestic policy developments relevant to soybean trade between Brazil and the EU. To that end, as part of CLEVER WP6 several model improvements have been conducted. Related developments conducted in CLEVER task 6.2 have already been described in D6.2, while additional developments under task 6.5 (value chain modeling at the actor level) are presented in this deliverable. This includes the following enhancements:

- Improve the representation of key land use policies in Brazil, and develop a parameterization of potential developments. The relationship between soy production and land use in Brazil is shaped by both public policies such as the Forest Code, and hybrid governance including commitments by private companies (e.g., Amazon Soy Moratorium). In addition, this environment might change in the long run, in particular in relation to EU unilateral interventions such as the EUDR: it may spur innovations and increased ambition in supply chain and land use governance in Brazil (with conservation benefits for Brazil ecosystems), or on the contrary lead to a dismantling of existing policies. The default model version does not include any representation of current policies and their potential evolution under alternative scenarios: we rely on the Brazil-zoomed version of GLOBIOM (Soterroni et al. 2018) to parameterize current policies, and develop parameterization for alternative scenarios inspired by the empirical evidence from WP5 and input from WP7 stakeholder consultations on soy supply chains (see D7.2 and D7.3).
- Improve the representation of soy cropping expansion. As detailed in D6.2, following (Soterroni et al. 2018) we introduced soy-corn double cropping as a new production system in Brazil. Here we describe additional efforts to parameterize over the 2000-2020 period at federal state-level the exogenous yield trends as well as the expansion of single soy and soy-corn double cropping system. We provide a comparison of calibrated vs observed trends over the 2000-2020 period, and a description of related parameterization after 2020.
- Develop a parameterization of key EU policies relevant to Brazil-EU trade of soya bean products. As part of the EU Green Deal Ambition, the EU recently adopted a new legislation regulating the imports of deforestation risks commodities, among which soy-based products. In addition, continued efforts to develop a Regional Trade Agreement between the EU and the MERCOSUR countries (including Brazil) may lead to its adoption and implementation in the coming years, with potential effects on soya trade. The default version of the model does not include any representation of such policy interventions, and we will rely on estimates from the literature, econometric estimates from CLEVER WP3 and empirical evidence from CLEVER WP5 to parameterize new scenarios for these policies.

- Improve the tracing of commodity flows and environmental impacts embedded in trade in the model, and develop a parameterization for an EU biodiversity border adjustment scenario. The implementation challenges associated with the EUDR are large, and even a perfectly implemented EUDR will not reduce all imported biodiversity impacts (such as the conversion of non-forest habitats to produce soya) Given the importance of trade in shaping global environmental impacts, it is important to better measure the biodiversity impacts imported through trade, and explore potential alternative approaches to their regulation, including price-based instruments such as border-adjustment mechanisms. While the model provides detailed and dynamic projections of commodity flows and related environmental impacts, an accurate accounting of the amount of primary commodities and environmental impacts embedded in trade was so far not available in the model. We will develop a dedicated commodity, land use and biodiversity impact footprint module, and we will then use it to parameterize an EU biodiversity border adjustment scenario.

Forest supply chains

As part of CLEVER WP7, we use the GLOBIOM model to quantitatively assess future scenarios on forest supply chains, designed to explore potential trade-offs for forest carbon stocks and terrestrial biodiversity of mobilizing forest biomass for climate mitigation purposes, accounting for alternative assumptions about forest management strategies, and an uptake of circular economy principles. To that end, as part of CLEVER WP6 several model improvements have been conducted. Related developments conducted in CLEVER task 6.2 have already been described in D6.2, while additional developments under tasks 6.4 (environmental and socio-economic trade-offs) & 6.5 (value chain modeling at the actor level) are presented in this deliverable. This includes the following enhancements:

- In order to better understand the potential trade-offs between biomass extraction and climate impacts, the dynamics of forest age structure (and related carbon stocks) in managed forests and carbon uptake in plantation forests were explicitly modeled, historical and future deforestation and afforestation trends were refined, an accounting of carbon stored in harvested wood products and bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS) systems was added, as well as an accounting of fossil fuel substitution effects.
- In order to better capture the potential for circular economy measures in relation to forest biomass supply chains, we parameterized a 'circular economy upscaling' scenario option through an increase in the maximum recycled wood collection rate in downstream sectors (from 50% to 75%), the possibility to re-use sawnwood as an alternative to recycling, and the exclusion of sawdust, woodchips and recycled wood from energy use (as an application of the cascading principle).
- To better understand the potential trade-offs between plantation forest development and biodiversity, a pool of abandoned agricultural land after year 2000 was separated from the non-forest natural vegetation land pool, dynamically adjusted as agricultural land is abandoned over time, and assumed to be of similar value for biodiversity than agricultural land. This allows to differentiate biodiversity impacts from plantation development over recently abandoned agricultural land from that of plantation development over mature non-forest natural vegetation.
- To better represent trends in the forestry sector as an actor in Europe and Brazil, we conducted selected improvements in the representation of possible alternative future trends in these regions, in particular in relation to expected conservation and restoration interventions. This choice echoes the high interest for such scenarios as expressed by forest supply chain stakeholders during our dedicated workshop.
- To better characterize the socio-economic impacts from the scenarios on the forestry as an aggregated actor in various regions, we developed an indicator of regional competitiveness based on the net trade of all wood products, aggregated in terms of roundwood equivalents.

Aquaculture and aquafeeds

As part of CLEVER WP7, we use the GLOBIOM model to quantitatively assess future scenarios on aquaculture and aquafeed supply chains, designed to explore the impact of a baseline development in the blue food sector and variations of key underlying assumptions, in relation to aquaculture-related practices (feed conversion efficiency, replacement of fish-based aquafeed by crop-based aquafeed, crop composition of crop aquafeed, growth of unfed aquaculture) as well as changes in fisheries management and consumer preferences for various blue food products. Related developments conducted in CLEVER task 6.2 have already been described in D6.2, while additional developments under task 6.5 (value chain modeling at the actor level) are presented in this deliverable. This includes the following enhancements:

- Improving baseline trends in the future development of unfed-aquaculture. In D6.2, we initially assumed that the capacity of unfed aquaculture would remain constant to 2020 levels after 2020. However, during the stakeholder workshop, this assumption was evaluated as pessimistic. To address this, we modified our baseline assumption to feature an increase in unfed aquaculture after 2020 that prolongates historical development.
- Parameterizing an alternative scenario picturing changes to the crop composition of crop aquafeed. In D6.2 the crop composition of aquafeed (i.e., the share of various crops in total crop aquafeed requirements), based on country-specific data from (Froehlich et al. 2018), was assumed constant over time in the baseline scenario. This was however identified as a potential source of uncertainty in the relationship between crop aquafeed requirements and related land use and biodiversity impacts. In order to explore this uncertainty, we therefore designed a scenario with a partial replacement of soy and corn by wheat in crop aquafeed for China, the region with largest projected future increases in fed aquaculture production.
- Parameterizing an alternative scenario for sustainable fisheries management. In D6.2, as well as D7.2 scenarios, we assumed the level of catches to remain constant at 2020 levels after 2020. However, this level of catch leads to about one third of fish stock being overfished, with risks for ocean ecosystems and food security. A transition to more sustainable fisheries management emerges from the literature and discussions during our stakeholder workshop as relevant element to consider. Elleby et al. (2025) recently estimated the global adoption of sustainable fisheries management to lead to a moderate increase in catch levels (despite an initial decrease for the catch of overfished stocks) over the following 3 decades. We used these estimates to test an explorative scenario in which the assumed global adoption of sustainable fisheries management leads to a moderate level of increases in catch levels after 2020.
- Parameterizing an alternative scenario for consumer preferences for blue food products. Consumer choices and related policies are recognized as an important lever for navigating future challenges related to food security and environmental impacts of food production (Gephart et al. 2021), with significant differences across aquaculture products in nutrition and environmental impact profiles (Gephart and Golden 2022). To explore related uncertainty, we designed a scenario in which the future level of freshwater fish consumption is partially replaced by mollusks, mostly sourced from unfed aquaculture and with consistently better nutritional and environmental impact performance than most freshwater species.

MODEL DEVELOPEMENTS

Soy supply chains

Representation of key land use policies in Brazil and alternative scenarios

Status quo

As part of an effort to improve the representation of land use dynamics in Brazil in the CLEVER project, various mechanisms to simulate the land-use restrictions and protection of forests and other natural areas in Brazil have been incorporated into GLOBIOM, largely based on the framework established by (Soterroni et al. 2018). These include representations of the Mata Atlântica law, the Brazilian Forest Code, the Amazon Soy Moratorium, and restrictions on agricultural expansion in the Caatinga biome. The introduction of these mechanisms into GLOBIOM provides a structured representation of forest protection policies and land-use restrictions in Brazil, simulating their implementation and effects within the model's framework.

Illegal deforestation control. Following (Soterroni et al. 2018), the Mata Atlântica law (law 11.428/2006) is implemented in the GLOBIOM model as a complete prohibition of deforestation in the Mata Atlântica biome from 2010 onwards. In other biomes, restrictions on deforestation under the Brazilian Forest Code apply from 2020 onwards. The Brazilian law 12.651/2012 mandates all rural properties to maintain an area covered by native vegetation, as a Legal Reserve, and provides a delineation between legal deforestation (i.e., where remaining forest remains above the Legal Reserve) and illegal deforestation (i.e., where remaining forest is below the Legal Reserve). In the model, legal deforestation is allowed as long as part of neither a restoration nor a compensation scheme (see next paragraph) while illegal deforestation allowed up to a certain amount determined by an assumed enforcement probability. This enforcement probability is zero in other biomes than the Amazon and the Cerrado biomes, where spatially-explicit values were estimated from historical data on policing deforestation and related costs.

Restoration of debts. Besides preventing future deforestation, the GLOBIOM model also accounts for the compensation of environmental debt arising from past illegal deforestation. This mechanism is structured around the Legal Reserve requirements and considers the Small Farms Amnesty, which exempts farms below regional size thresholds from compensating for pre-2008 deforestation (Guidotti et al. 2017). Compensation for environmental debt is fulfilled through Environmental Reserve Quotas (*Cotas de Reserva Ambiental*, CRA). The model assumes that surplus forest from other simulation units within the same biome may compensate for this debt, with the exception that only 20% of the surplus forest in the federal state of Amazonas is eligible. This limitation reflects the assumption from (Soterroni et al. 2018) that only 20% of unclaimed public lands in this state will be designated as private properties and thus enter the CRA system. It also safeguards that the large forest surpluses from this state cannot compensate all forest debt within the Amazonia biome. In GLOBIOM, surplus forest is distributed across simulation units within a biome, prioritizing those with the greatest deforestation debt. The unit with the largest debt absorbs as much of the surplus as possible before the remaining surplus is allocated to the next most indebted unit, continuing until either all debt or all surplus is exhausted. The same logic applies to assigning deforestation debt to units with surplus forest, but here the allocation is capped at a fraction of each unit's forest surplus to ensure a broader

distribution of the burden. After this process, any remaining debt must be repaid through reforestation during the 2030 simulation period. This reforestation is modelled as the conversion of former cropland (used only for sugarcane and soybean production) or pastureland into protected forest. Once reforested, the land remains protected in all subsequent simulation periods.

Amazon Soy Moratorium. The Amazon Soy Moratorium is a voluntary agreement established in 2006 by major soybean traders to prevent deforestation in the Amazon biome for soybean cultivation. Under the moratorium, traders commit to not purchase soy grown on land deforested after July 2008 in the Amazon, using satellite monitoring to enforce compliance. The moratorium is modelled by restricting soybean cultivation in the Amazon biome from 2020 onwards to land already used for growing soy in 2010, the previous simulation period. This timing was selected due to the model's 10-year simulation intervals, with the closest reference year being 2010. The restriction is applied uniformly across all simulation units in the biome. Under this mechanism, the total area of soybean cultivation in the biome remains fixed at 2010 levels, while production increases remain possible via yield trends and endogenous shifts to more efficient management practices.

Limitations to agricultural land expansion in the Caatinga biome. In addition, the GLOBIOM model limits cropland and grassland expansion in the Caatinga biome based on (Soterroni et al. 2018) to match the historical trends of these landcovers driven by local water scarcity and uncertainty. This corresponds to a maximal expansion of both landcovers of 10% per 10-year simulation period.

Parameterization of alternative scenarios

While by default the above-mentioned policies are assumed to remain active after 2020 in the mode, we developed a parameterization of two contrasted options for the evolution of such policies:

- In the Zero Natural Land (ZNL_Bra) scenario, these policies are assumed to be significantly increased in ambition, leading conversion of forest and non-forest natural land to agricultural land to halt in Brazil after 2020. This is implemented as a complete restriction of any conversion of natural land to agricultural land in Brazil. Rather than a realistic policy development, this scenario intends to capture the boundary conditions of Brazil's soy sector. While it may be interpreted as an upper bound estimate of a what a positive spillover of EU policies could be, it should be noted that it goes way beyond the EUDR in terms of ambition.
- In the Weak Land Use Regulation (WeakLUR) scenario, conservation and land use governance are assumed to be weakened after 2020, through a removal of the Amazon Soy Moratorium and a weakening of the Forest Code. From 2030 onwards, the constraint preventing the expansion of soy area in the Amazon (assumed as part of the current governance, see above) is deactivated. In addition, from 2030 onwards, the enforcement probabilities for illegal deforestation control as part of the Forest Code are reduced by a factor of 3 in both the Amazonia and Cerrado biomes.

Improvement of soy cropping system expansion

As detailed in deliverable D6.2, we introduced several changes to the representation of soy production systems in Brazil to better represent their dynamics in terms of area expansion and production volumes at subnational level. This included the introduction of a soy-corn double cropping system (in addition to single soy cropping systems), the increase of the spatial resolution of land use and soy production system area variables to 30 arcminute grid cells, the initialization of related biophysical parameters (e.g., soya and corn yields and input requirements) by production system and grid cell with estimates from the EPIC crop model generated in CLEVER (see D6.1), the initialization of the spatial distribution of land uses and soy planted areas by production system and grid cell with municipality-level data from Brazilian remote sensing products and statistics, and the calibration of planted area expansion rate parameters at the state-level.

Since D6.2, additional developments have taken place towards the same objective. First, the parameterization of historical yield trends (2000-2020) was adjusted: instead of national level trends for all production systems, we introduced state-level and production system-specific (i.e., single soy vs soy-corn double cropping) trends derived from municipal-level Brazilian statistics. After 2020, national yield trends from the SSP2 scenario apply on top of the state-level 2020/2000 yields trends. Second, we subsequently re-estimated the calibration of state-level parameters for the planted area expansion of individual soy production systems. Third, we also specified a set of simple rules for the post-2020 evolution of the planted area expansion rate parameters, based on an analysis of historical values: a) the rate of soy-corn double cropping expansion per decade decreases as the share of this system in total soy harvested area in previous time step increases, b) the rate of expansion of single soy production system per decade converges to a value of +50%, with a speed that increases with the expansion rate value from the previous time step.

Results are shown in Figure 1 for soy harvested area and production volume by production system at the state level for 2000, 2010 and 2020, and in Figure 2 in terms of 2000-2020 trends in specific dimensions (total soy harvested area, share of double cropping within soy harvested area, yield, production) of soy production systems at the biome level. The main historical developments of harvested areas and yields by production system at the state-level are broadly captured, despite deviations to statistical data at the level of individual states, production system and time horizons. Overall, the model captures relatively well biome-level trends in the share of soy-corn double cropping and in soy yields, the predominance of area expansion in various determining production increases, and the importance of a few states (Mata Grosso, Parana, Rio Grande Do Sul, Minas Gerais, Sao Paulo, Bahia) for soy production. Deviations include for example a moderate overestimation of the relative increase in harvested area and production in the Cerrado biome, and moderate underestimation of the harvested area and production expansion in the Pampa and Amazone biomes.

Deviations to the observations can be explained by several reasons. First, despite the improvement of some parameter estimates through revised input data and calibration, several parameters (e.g., differences across grid cells within a state in yields, or in the maximum rate of harvested area expansion by cropping system) remain weakly constrained and/or informed by

datasets from various sources that are not necessarily fully consistent (e.g., soy yields from EPIC and municipal-level harvested area statistics, see D6.1). Second, there are trade-offs in the choice of best parameter at the calibration stage, for example between outcome variables (i.e., harvested area vs production) or between time horizons (e.g., 2010 vs 2020). For these two sources of deviation, a better fit to observation might be achieved via increasing the number of parameters calibrated, or calibrate different values for different time horizons. However, such improved behavior over recent historical period might not necessarily lead to a more realistic simulation of future trends.

As shown for example by the underestimation of increases in soy harvested area in the Amazon biome from 2010 to 2020, our assumed effect of Amazon Soy Moratorium (no increase in harvested area after 2010, see previous section) might be optimistic, and a better fit could be achieved by using a slightly more permissive development of soy area in the Amazon. It should however be noted that the deviation represents a small absolute area.

Additional improvements could potentially be achieved by using the TRASE dataset to impose a structural relationship between the volume exports to specific countries to production patterns at the simulation unit level (i.e., a specific distribution of market shares within). However, this type of relationship might represent quite a structural change in the formulation of the model, possibly affecting several aspects of the model calibration and performance. In addition, it is not clear how much improvement this could bring as compared to the calibration described above. Moreover, there is limited evidence on how such market shares evolve over future temporal horizons (e.g., to 2050) and scenarios (including significant changes in land use regulation), especially given the very dynamic developments expected in the baseline and the nature of the scenarios considered in WP7. While such questions are explored in CLEVER WP3, the time span over which the TRASE data is available (2005-2022) is only about half of the 2020-2050 temporal horizon we consider in WP7. Finally, this would also require a significant modification of the footprinting module developed as part of CLEVER T6.5 (see last section on model developments for soy supply chains). Altogether, these challenges were evaluated as too large for pursuing such an option in the frame of the CLEVER project.

Figure 1 - Comparison of observed (IBGE-PAM) and simulated (GLOBIOM) harvested areas (in million ha) and production volume (in million t) by soy production systems and state over 2000-2020

Figure 2 - Comparison of observed (IBGE PAM) vs simulated (GLOBIOM) trends in various aspects (harvested area, production volume, yield and share of soy-corn double cropping in total harvested area) of soy production systems over 2000-2020 at the biome level. For each aspect and biome, values are time horizon- and source-specific (i.e., observed vs simulated) values normalized by the value for year 2000 in the observation dataset.

Parameterization of EUDR and EU-MERCOSUR scenarios

The assessment of the potential impacts of the EU Deforestation Regulation (EUDR) and the EU-Mercosur Agreement (EUM) on Brazil's soy exports to the EU relies on a combination of quantitative econometrics modelling, literature review, and stakeholder insights gathered during the soy online workshop of 14 May 2025.

The core of the analysis is based on a structural gravity model, which is used to estimate the magnitude of the impacts of the EUDR and the EUM on Brazil's soy exports to the EU, as well as any broader spillovers on trade flows. This approach allows for a consistent and theory-based estimation of trade impacts across different policy scenarios. Further technical details on the modelling approach can be found in (Ringwald 2025).

A summary of the method used to estimate the impacts of the EUDR, EUM and their combination (EUM+EUDR) on Brazil's soy exports to the EU, and the parametrization of these estimates into the GLOBIOM model is provided below. These estimates have been used to design new scenarios for the CLEVER deliverable D7.3, looking at the impact of new EU trade-related policies on Brazil-EU soy trade and associated biodiversity impacts.

EU Deforestation Regulation (EUDR)

The EUDR is a new kind of trade-related policy, which is expected to be implemented from December 2025. This poses challenges in providing an estimate of its potential impact on trade due to the absence of trade policy data.

One possible approach in empirical analysis is to use historical precedents as proxy to the trade policy under investigation. (Wolfmayr et al. 2024), for instance, used the EU Timber Regulation (EUTR) – which aimed to counter trade in illegally harvested timber - as a proxy for the EUDR. They first estimated the effect of the EUTR on trade in timber products and then applied this estimate to the products covered by the EUDR.¹ They found a marginal effect on trade flows of -0.13%. This method has been replicated for soybeans, as presented on the table in Annex.

Here we use the estimate from (Wolfmayr et al. 2024) as a lower bound and consider the trade effect of the EUDR to be larger than that of the EUTR, mainly due to foreseen higher compliance costs associated with more stringent requirements (Köthke et al. 2023). Specifically, we assume that compliance with the EUDR requirements² leads to additional costs of ~3% of the soybean price (Stam 2024)³, which are then passed through to EU consumers. As our estimated trade

¹ The EUTR has now been repealed by the EUDR.

² Operators in scope of the regulation must demonstrate that the commodities they place on the EU market have been produced on land that was not subject to deforestation (after 31 December 2020) and have been produced in accordance with relevant laws applicable in the country of production by undertaking due diligence on their supply chain.

³ (Stam 2024) estimated through a test run that compliance with the EUDR (incl. segregation, tracking and due diligence procedures) leads to additional cost of EUR 32/ton for Brazilian soy or around 6% of the soybean price – provided that all Brazilian soy was exported to the EU. Considering each Brazilian States share of exports to the EU, this results in additional cost ranging from 0.3% to 4% of the soy price.

cost elasticity for soybean is larger than 1% (see table 1), this translates into a ~3% reduction in total trade flows from Brazil to the EU.

This 3% reduction in trade flows is implemented into GLOBIOM as a tax on EU imports of Brazil's soy-based products from 2020 onwards, equivalent to 3% of the EU price in 2020. This corresponds to absolute tax levels of 9, 6 and 36 USD2000/ton for soybean, soy cake and soy oil, respectively. As derived through sensitivity analysis, these tax levels lead to a 3% decline in Brazil's exports of soy-based products (i.e., soybean, soy oil and soy protein meal) to the EU compared to what is projected in the SSP2 baseline scenario.

EU-Mercosur trade agreement (EUM)

In empirical analysis, the potential effect of two economies entering a trade agreement is drawn from the variation of other countries having entered such or similar agreements and their conditional change in the responding trade volume (Ringwald 2025). Using this method (with data for soybean trade for 1991-2018), indicates a large increase in soy trade volumes following the entry into application of a trade agreement, in the magnitude of +78%.

Econometric modeling is complemented by a review of available estimates from the literature (see Table 1). Overall, estimates of the effects on trade volumes of entering into a trade agreement show important variation both in terms of magnitude and direction of impact, depending on the sample (both in terms of timespan covered and the set of trading partners represented), data sources, as well as general modelling and estimation techniques. This highlights the challenge in finding robust estimates of trade agreement proxy effects but also of trade elasticity or tariff effects from product-level trade flow data.

Finally, the estimation strategy also reflects feedback received during the online workshop. Soy and agricultural experts considered the initial estimate of the impact of the EUM on Brazil-EU soy trade to be too high (+78%) given that tariff levels for soy are already low. Consequently, the initial estimate has been revised downward (to mainly capture the indirect effect from trade integration), and a more conservative estimate of a 20% increase in Brazil's soy exports to the EU is now considered.

The above estimate is implemented in GLOBIOM as a subsidy on EU imports of Brazil's soy-based products from 2020 onwards, equivalent to 25% of the EU price in 2020. This corresponds to absolute subsidy levels of 67, 40 and 259 USD2000/ton for soybean, soy cake and soy oil, respectively. As derived through sensitivity analysis, these subsidy levels lead to a 20% increase in Brazil's exports of soy-based products (i.e., soybean, soy oil and soy protein meal) to the EU compared to what is projected in the SSP2 baseline scenario.

Combination of EUDR and EUM

During the online workshop, stakeholders also expressed interest in understanding the interactions between the EUDR and EUM. Rather than only focusing on the individual impact of each policy, many were interested in understanding the combined effect - and whether trade

liberalization under the EUM could be offset, or even undermined, by the additional compliance costs introduced by the EUDR.

Estimating this interaction is difficult, including due to challenges in estimating the impact of single policies. However, estimating the interaction between the trade cost elasticity (EUDR proxy) with the trade agreement (EUM proxy) term suggests that sensitivity to trade costs increases (see last row in Table 1). Therefore, we assume that the combination of EUM and EUDR might slightly exacerbate the costs associated with EUDR and therefore its negative impact on Brazil's soy exports to the EU (i.e., with reduction around -5% compared to -3% assumed in the EUDR scenario), leading to an overall 15% increase in trade (compared to 20% for EUM alone).

The above estimate is implemented in GLOBIOM as a subsidy on EU imports of Brazil's soy-based products from 2020 onwards, equivalent to 17% of the EU price in 2020. This corresponds to absolute subsidy levels of 46, 27 and 176 USD2000/ton for soybean, soy cake and soy oil, respectively. As derived through sensitivity analysis, these subsidy levels lead to a 15% increase in Brazil's exports of soy-based products (i.e., soybean, soy oil and soy protein meal) to the EU compared to what is projected in the SSP2 baseline scenario.

Table 1. Trade elasticity, trade agreement and EUDR proxy effects

Product	Timeframe	Trade Elasticity (tariff rate)		Trade Agreement Effect		EUDR Proxy Effect		Source
		Parameter	Effect	Parameter	Effect	Parameter	Effect	
Soybeans	2000–2019	-5.826***/ -5.879***	-5.37%/ -5.42%	-0.186/ -0.157	-18.6%/ -15.7%	-	-	Table 2. in [1]
Soybeans	1990–2019	-	-	0.05	0.051%	-	-	Table 3 in [2]
Timber	1992–2019	-	-	-0.0142	-1.41%	-0.0013***	-0.13%	Table 4.13 in [3]
Oilseeds	1985–2000	-	-	[0.51,1.7]	[66.5%, 447.4%]	-	-	Table 7 in [4]
Soybeans	1991–2018	-1.295***	-1.29%	0.612***	84.3%	-	-	Own calculations (PPML)
Soybeans	1991–2018	-1.088***	-1.08%	0.581***	78.8%	-1.036***	-64.5%	Own calculations with rough EUTR proxy (PPML)
Soybeans	1991–2018	-1.299***/ -1.394 (with TA interaction)	-1.29%/ -1.38% (with TA interaction)	0.644***	90.4%	-	-	Own calculations with TA & tariff interaction after the (PPML)

Note: Estimates from the literature (row 1–4) and own calculations (row 5–7). The "Parameter" columns report estimated coefficients from structural gravity model regressions. The "Effect" column translates each estimate into its implied impact on bilateral trade flows. Due to the log-linear specification of the gravity model, coefficients on continuous variables can be interpreted as elasticities (i.e., the percentage change in trade from a 1% change in the variable). For dummy variables, the effect represents the percentage difference in trade flows relative to the baseline, calculated as $e^{\beta} - 1$. This structure allows a direct interpretation of how trade frictions or agreements influence trade volumes.

Sources: [1] (Dhoubhadel et al. 2023); [2] (Dadakas et al. 2025); [3] (Wolfmayr et al. 2024); [4] (Jayasinghe and Sarker 2008)

EU biodiversity border adjustment mechanism and footprinting

The EUDR focuses on reducing the amount of deforestation imported to the EU: while deforestation is an important contribution to biodiversity loss, this approach may even enhance important biodiversity impacts through the conversion of other non-forest ecosystems. Moreover, as illustrated in the deliverable D7.2, reaching global biodiversity goals will likely require not only limiting the loss of natural land, but also significant restoration efforts, which might more directly conflict with soy production expansion in Brazil than halting the loss of forest and non-forest natural land. In addition, the successful implementation of the EUDR will require significant innovations in supply chain management aspects such as data collection, traceability and risk management. While achieving those will benefit supply chain management possibilities globally, this could also create significant challenges to a successful implementation of the EUDR.

For all the above reasons, it is worth exploring the impact of alternative approaches in reducing imported biodiversity impacts to the EU. One such option could be a biodiversity border adjustment mechanism, explicitly targeting biodiversity impacts. Such an option could be made possible by developments in supply chain data, allowing the estimation of relatively simple measures of biodiversity impacts per unit of product produced at country level for a broad range of commodities. To explore scenarios picturing such a development, we developed a footprinting module in GLOBIOM, and used to design a biodiversity border adjustment mechanism.

Footprinting module and biodiversity loss embedded in trade

The GLOBIOM model provides estimate of market balances at the regional and commodity level (including bilateral trade between regions), various supply chain steps at regional level (e.g., crushing of oilseed crops into vegetable oils and protein meals, use of grass, crops and protein meals as livestock feed), as well as resource and input use associated to the production of primary products at a high spatial resolution within regions. We used this information to estimate the amount of primary product embedded in the supply, processing, trade and final consumption of all agricultural products and regions covered in the model, as well as associated environment impacts (e.g., land use and subsequent biodiversity loss from land occupation).

To do so, we developed a commodity footprinting module, providing for each time and scenario an accounting of primary products (crops and grass) embedded in the trade, processing and consumption of intermediate (crops, protein meals and distiller grains, vegetable oils) and final (crops, vegetable oils, livestock products, biofuels) product, from the region of primary product production to the place of transformation into intermediate and final product, and the place of consumption. Based on the simulated endogenous model variables, the module first estimates for both primary and transformed commodities the amount of product re-exports (imports to a region re-exported to another) and reallocates them as a direct export from the source region to the destination region following the method from (Kastner et al. 2011). For every supply chain transformation step in the model (i.e., conversion of feed to livestock products, crushing of oilseed crops to vegetable oil and protein meals, biofuel production from vegetable oils and starch/sugar crops), the input is allocated to the various output products based on the share of

each individual output in total outputs, measured in either protein content (for livestock products) or energetic content (for crushing and biofuel production, based on lower heating values).

The commodity footprints are then transformed into environmental footprints. Land use footprints are obtained by multiplying at regional level the amount of primary product embedded in commodity flows by the average land requirements per ton of primary product in the source region, based on the gridded distribution of crop and grass harvested area and yields simulated by the model. Similarly, biodiversity impact footprints from land occupation are calculated, based on the same information combined with the gridded distribution of land occupation characterization factors (based on (UNEP/SETAC 2016), as provided for the cSARUS16 model in (Leclère et al. 2020). Both the commodity and the environmental impacts are calculated in between each time step within a scenario, allowing the estimates to dynamically reflect simulated changes in markets, technologies and land allocation. This also allows using the footprints calculated in a time step to affect variables in the subsequent time step (see next section).

As an illustration, Figure 3 provides the marginal land occupation-related biodiversity impacts (global species loss, in potentially disappeared fraction per year per ton of fresh matter produced, pdf/yr/t) associated with the production of two different crops (soy and wheat) production in three regions over time. These values reflect multiple factors, such as differences across and within regions in local original species richness, its sensitivity to cropland use, where various crops are grown, and yield levels. These factors can evolve over time. For example, the marginal impact associated to soya production in the EU27 decreases after 2020 as a result of production partially moving from Italy to France and Croatia (where marginal impacts are much lower than in Italy), while marginal impacts for soya production are decreasing in Brazil over 2000-2020 as a result of changes to the subnational allocation of soy harvested areas in Brazil and the development of soy-corn double cropping. As a result, marginal impacts from soya production are larger in Brazil than in the EU except for the 2010-2020 period, and marginal impacts from soya production in the USA are always lower than both. These results illustrate the impacts of production systems dynamics at subnational level in shaping biodiversity impacts. It should also be noted that the choice of impact pathways is important as well: here only the land occupation impacts are considered, and accounting for example for land transformation impacts as well would likely make estimates for Brazil more robustly higher than for the EU and the USA, and can be done in the model. It should also be noted that uncertainties associated with the choice of the method for estimated biodiversity impacts are likely important as well, as for example illustrated in CLEVER Deliverable D6.4.

Marginal land occupation biodiversity impact of soya bean production
(selected regions, SSP2 scenario)

Figure 3 - Projections for marginal land occupation-related biodiversity impact on terrestrial ecosystems associated to soya bean production for selected regions, in potentially disappeared fraction per year per ton of fresh matter harvested. Note the y-axis unit: impacts displayed range from 1 to 10 E-12 pdf / yr / t.

It should be noted that, for specific commodities and countries, it might be possible to do a more detailed footprinting, by using available data sources to estimate where, within a country, the production associated to each destination country is located. This could for example be possible for soy-based commodities in Brazil, by using the TRASE dataset, as for example done in (Soterroni et al. 2019), and allow a richer analysis of the role of various actors along the supply chains (including by distinguishing various traders). Such data is, however, only available for very few countries and commodities, which does not allow for a comprehensive coverage of commodities covered in the model, or even of key soy producing regions. This is particularly important when it comes to the development of scenarios like a border adjustment mechanism (see below). In addition, even in the best cases, such dataset does not have sufficiently long time series to provide reliable estimates of the stationarity in time of such relationship and their potential response to the scenarios we consider in WP7.

Parameterization of an EU biodiversity border adjustment mechanism

We used the footprinting module to parameterize a scenario representing an EU biodiversity border adjustment mechanism. Such an intervention is assumed to take the form of a tax applied to EU imports of selected high-risk agricultural commodities covered in the model (soya-based products, oil palm-based products and bovine meat), proportional to the difference in marginal land occupation-related biodiversity impact (see above) as compared to that of the EU27.

As detailed in Equ. [1], the tax $T(p,R,t)$ at a given time t applied to a given product p imported from a source region R only applies to cases where imports have higher land occupation-related marginal impact $b(p,R,t)$ than that of the EU27 $b(p,EU27,t)$ (i.e., no subsidy to imports of soya from places where marginal impact is lower than in the EU), and its level is proportional to the difference between the marginal impact in the source region at the previous time step $t-1$, and to the economic value associated to biodiversity loss $E(t)$ for a given time horizon t .

$$\text{Equ. [1]} \quad T(p,R,t) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } b(p,R,t) \leq b(p,EU27,t) \\ [b(p,R,t) - b(p,EU27,t)] * E(t) & \text{if } b(p,R,t) > b(p,EU27,t) \end{cases}$$

The marginal biodiversity impact $b(p,R,t)$ is estimated from the result of the footprinting module at previous time step (i.e., 2020 for 2030, etc.), and the tax is applied from 2030 onwards in the relevant scenarios. The economic value associated to biodiversity loss $E(t)$ is assumed to be based on an estimate of the global economic value of ecosystem services provided by nature E_0 , with a progressive progression between 2030 and 2050 ($E(t)$ equals 5%, 50% and 100% of E_0 in respectively 2030, 2040 and 2050). For E_0 , we used the estimate of (Costanza et al. 2014) of 125 trillion USD/year. This can be considered a low- to middle-range estimate of the economic value of nature (from an instrumental perspective), with recent estimates ranging from 44 trillion USD/year (World Economic Forum estimate of the economic output of all sectors moderately to highly dependent on nature⁴) to 179 trillion USD/year (Boston Consulting Group estimate of the value of all ecosystem services⁵), and the understanding that such estimates do not capture all forms of contributions from nature to human wellbeing (O'Brian et al. 2025). In the virtual case where all terrestrial biodiversity is lost through land use (potentially disappeared fraction per year = 1), and the outputs of all related activities were taxed (not just the imports to the EU), the value of the tax collection would equal 125 trillion USD/year, which is also equivalent to slightly more than 1 year of gross domestic product.

It should be noted that we choose to focus on land occupation impacts alone, which can be interpreted as the biodiversity opportunity costs of not restoring the underlying land use. This choice explicitly reflects two main considerations. First, reaching overarching goal global biodiversity goals from the Kunming-Montreal Global biodiversity framework of 'bending the curve' will require significant restoration, and that in the context of soy production regions, including Brazil, such a restoration may be more directly in conflict with increasing soy production than halting natural land loss (see also CLEVER Deliverable D7.2). Other choices could here be considered relevant, such as for example basing the tax on the sum land occupation and

⁴ (World Economic Forum 2020)

⁵ (Oğuz 2025)

land transformation impacts: this would put also an emphasis on halting the loss of natural land, in addition to restoration efforts. However, this leads to our second consideration: land occupation impacts are easier to measure for a broad range of commodities than land transformation impacts, which requires not only mapping land use activities, but also mapping land use changes and allocating those to land use activities. A tax scheme that includes land transformation impacts might therefore be considered less likely to occur.

Note on the use of TRASE data for detailed modeling at actor level

The initial task description envisaged that the TRASE dataset be used for refined actor level modeling for soy supply chains in Brazil in GLOBIOM (e.g., adding subnational-scale heterogeneity in the destination of production, explicitly representing traders as a step in supply chains). In particular, based on a combination of data collection at municipal level and supply chain modeling, the TRASE dataset provides information such as market shares (i.e., the volume of soy produced and destined to export in various countries), which is not available from global data sources used to build the model: incorporating it can allow new types of modeling. However, doing it in addition to the other model developments for the soy supply chains described earlier in this section was going beyond the resources of the project. We provide here a suggestion of potential ways forward for various purposes, and the challenges implied:

- **Introducing heterogeneity in the destination of production at subnational level:** by default, in GLOBIOM the relationship between the allocation of production to various subnational scale units (e.g., 30 arcminutes grid for Brazil) in a region and the allocation of its commodity-specific total exports to various other model regions is governed by a few factors, such as the impact of export destination on the value of total export and the subnational distribution of production potential and associated production costs. E.g., the higher the value of export increase in a time step, the higher the marginal production cost increase, which mobilizes additional production options from subnational production units previously not competitive. However, the realized production and export patterns may not be consistent with actual market shares at subnational level, and data on the latter could be used to constrain the model for a more realistic markets shares, which could in turn support a more realistic estimate of the simulated relationship between exports to various destinations and land resource use aspects such as land use change, and related simulated footprints embedded in international soy-based supply chains. There could be various ways to implement in the model, such as introducing an additional constraint equations imposing a relationship between the volume of soy-based product export to various destinations and the soy total production volume in subnational production spatial units, or differentiating exports to various countries as separate commodities with distinct production patterns. This could also be used in the footprinting module to allocate footprints from Brazil soy production to various exporters at subnational level. This however requires careful and time-consuming exploration, as several challenges need to be overcome. In particular, this type of relationship needs to cover the entire time span of the simulations (from the year 2000 to the year 2050), in order to be properly included in the model calibration and structurally consistent over the entire simulation. A detailed calibration of related parameters (across subnational production units and time steps) could be needed to match historical trends given the dynamic nature of soy supply chains over the recent

past, and could influence other calibration steps mentioned in the previous sections. Projections to 2050 represent a much larger time span than the availability of TRASE data, and assumptions about typical changes of market shares at a decadal time step would involve large extrapolations.

- **Introducing additional constraints reflecting the impact of importer policies on land use patterns.** Once heterogeneity in the destination of production at subnational level has been introduced, this may support a finer modeling of importer policies. For example, the EUDR aims to eliminate legal deforestation in EU supply chains, and the representation of market shares at subnational production level could be used to endogenously limit possible deforestation outcomes in relation to the EU market share. Several points however need exploration, for example about how to deal with the very prevalent case of subnational production units for which EU market share is not dominating. This may be informed by the type of empirical knowledge generated in CLEVER WP3, but would need a more intensive collaboration than foreseen in CLEVER. In addition, it needs to be clarified how such a modeling feature would interact with the features introduced in earlier sections to model the impact of EUDR, and how to avoid double counting.
- **Introducing traders as explicit actors in the model.** Once heterogeneity in the destination of production at subnational level included in the model based on TRASE data, it may be possible to exploit the differentiation of market share by trader in that dataset to separate soy-based product production and export patterns by trader. The TRASE-derived shares could be implemented through either a simple allocation posterior to the model solve, or endogenous disaggregation of the trade variable by exporter complemented with additional equations for related market shares at subnational production spatial unit level. While finer scenarios could then be build on the response to policies of supply chains associated to various traders (e.g., compliance to EUDR for some traders, non-compliance for others), this would remain contingent to a successful inclusion of markets shares in the model, require a more intensive collaboration with WP3 than foreseen, and would likely require significantly more stakeholder engagement.

Forest supply chains

Age-class dynamics and forest management

In order to better represent forest carbon stock dynamics, we further refined the representation of forest management by explicitly modeling the dynamics of different age-class cohorts. Forest age-class dynamics in GLOBIOM works similarly than in large-scale area-based matrix models such as the European Forestry Dynamics Model (EFDM) (Packalen et al. 2014) or the European Forest Information Scenario Model (EFISCEN)(Schelhaas et al. 2007). The main difference between GLOBIOM and these models is that harvest decisions and age-class dynamics are based on economic optimization instead of statistical transition probabilities.

In GLOBIOM, the choice over different management systems and age-classes is made separately for each grid. Each grid consists of multiple even-aged stands which are divided to different age-cohorts. Biomass growth happens through age-class dynamics where after each period the stand area is moved to the next age-cohort. The biomass in each age-cohort follows S-shaped growth curves which are determined by the Chapman-Richards biomass growth model, as in (Humpenöder et al. 2014) and (Mishra et al. 2021). If the stand area is harvested or damaged by natural mortality, then it is moved in the first age-cohort. Since the size of the stand is not defined explicitly, the age-class dynamics can be interpreted either as even-or uneven aged managements.

Figure 4 displays an example of age-class dynamics in GLOBIOM. In 2020, the carbon stock of forests is calibrated to (FAO 2020) data and downscaled to grid level by utilizing G4M data and global age-class database (Besnard et al. 2021). After 2020, the carbon stock is determined endogenously by the age-class dynamics. The carbon stock of forests is higher in 2100 than in 2020, because the estimated biomass growth exceeds the estimated biomass removals from the forests (harvests, mortality) during this period.

Figure 4. Global carbon stock of forests divided by age-classes in the BASE scenario (excluding primary forests)

In GLOBIOM, forests are divided into three classes: 1) Plantation forests, 2) Seminatural forests and 3) Natural forests. Within each forest class there are different management systems as showed in Table 2. Forest management systems in GLOBIOM. The current formulation of the model includes 9 forest management systems.

Table 2. Forest management systems in GLOBIOM

Management	Description	Forest type	Management intensity	Calibration
CurC_H	Coniferous plantation forest	Plantation forest	3PGmix short rotation	FRA2020+Lesiv2022 plantation forest area
CurNC_H	Non-coniferous plantation forest	Plantation forest	3PGmix short rotation	FRA2020+Lesiv2022 plantation forest area
CurC	Coniferous production forest	Semi-natural forest	G4M EU 75-100% ROW 50-100 %	FRA2020+Lesiv2022 production forest area
CurNC	Non-coniferous production forest	Semi-natural forest	G4M EU 75-100% ROW 50-100 %	FRA2020+Lesiv2022 production forest area
CurC_M	Coniferous multifunctional forest	Semi-natural forest	G4M EU 50-75% ROW 25-50 %	FRA2020+Lesiv2022 production forest area
CurNC_M	Non-coniferous multifunctional forest	Semi-natural forest	G4M EU 50-75% ROW 25-50 %	FRA2020+Lesiv2022 production forest area
CurC_L	Coniferous close-to-nature forest	Natural forest	G4M EU 0-50% ROW 0-25 %	WDPA categories IV-VI
CurNC_L	Non-coniferous close-to-nature forest	Natural forest	G4M EU 0-50% ROW 0-25 %	WDPA categories IV-VI
CurS	Strictly protected secondary forest	Natural forest	0%	WDPA categories I-III
Cur0	Unprotected secondary forest	Natural forest	0%	Residual forest area
PriFor	Primary forest	Natural forest	0%	FRA2020+Lesiv2022 primary forest area, EU Sabatini map

Note: 1) Management intensity=% share of G4M maximum sustainable harvest potential based on NNP maps, local tree species and rotation time that maximizes increment given than carbon stock stays at the current level.

2) The model can choose between coniferous and non-coniferous management option in the limits of tree species distribution based on FRA2020 data (FAO 2020). In the EU, the model use additional grid level data on tree species from (Brus et al. 2012).

The transition from natural or semi-natural forests to planted forest happens through intensive management, i.e., removing old trees by harvesting and planting new ones. The transition from planted forests to natural or semi-natural forests happens through extensive management, i.e., removing old trees by harvesting or through natural mortality and waiting for new trees to appear by natural regeneration.

The spatially explicit biophysical data for each grid is based on the G4M forest management simulation model (Kinderman et al. 2006,2008). G4M provides GLOBIOM estimates on initial biomass stock, growing stock and sustainable level of harvests (=increment). Using the G4M data

and global age-class database (Besnard et al. 2021), the model generates grid level biomass growth curves, i.e., biomass and growing stocks for different stands within each grid.

Within each grid the model can have different management systems with different age-class dynamics, mortality and harvest intensity. The initial areas of different management systems are calibrated to the FRA (2020) data, the World Database of protect areas data (protected planet 2025) and the Global Forest Management Map (Lesiv et al. 2022). Moreover, for the historical periods 2000-2020 the management areas are matched to FAOSTAT country-level harvest volumes data (FAOSTAT 2025a).

After 2020, the age-class dynamics develops endogenously based on periodic harvests volumes, growth curves, mortality and forest area changes (deforestation/afforestation). To maintain the sustainability of harvest volumes over time in the recursive dynamics, the model includes two additional constraints. First, for each grid cell, the amount of harvested biomass cannot exceed biomass growth. Second, it is not allowed to harvest age-classes that are younger than the optimal rotation time. Optimal rotation times for natural/seminatural forests vary between 30-80 years depending on the management system and climate zone while for plantation forests between 5-30 years.

Finally, the initial calibration of the model for the historical period 2000-2020 has been improved to better match better harvest volumes data (FAOSTAT, 2025), forest biomass stocks and carbon emissions data (FAO 2020) and forest areas and land-use changes data (FAO 2020).

Plantation carbon uptake

Plantation carbon uptake is based on 3PGmix data (see D6.2) and calculated as additional carbon uptake relative to initial land use. Plantation carbon storage is 1/3-1/5 of natural forest carbon storage due to shorter rotation time and continuous logging. Cropland and (managed) grassland carbon storages are usually lower than plantations storage while other natural vegetation land carbon storage is higher than plantations storage. Most plantations are located in cropland, grassland and abandoned land (see D7.2), which implies that plantation carbon uptake is usually positive.

Deforestation and afforestation

In historical periods 2000-2020, deforestation and afforestation areas are based on (FAO 2020) country level data, which is allocated in the grid level according to GLOBIOM land-use dynamics. The land-use dynamics is based on land-use change costs, land suitability maps, production potential maps and demand for land on food, feed and fiber production (IBF-IIASA 2023).

After 2020, deforestation area is endogenous and depends on food and feed demand as well as carbon tax on deforestation emissions. Because carbon prices are relatively high in RCP1p9 scenario, there is very little deforestation after 2020 (Figure 5). It is important to mention that the conversion of natural forests to plantations is excluded in the model, i.e., the motive for deforestation in the model is food and feed demand instead of timber demand or some other reason (FAO 2020).

After 2020, afforestation area is based on G4M SSP2 RCP1p9 country level scenario data, which is allocated at the grid level according to GLOBIOM land-use dynamics. Afforestation competes with energy crops plantations, forest plantations and food production on the same marginal land areas. The difference between afforestation and forest plantations is that afforested areas are managed for carbon sequestration and nature conservation while forest plantations area managed for production use. There is also some differences in afforestation and plantations land suitability maps, i.e., some areas are suitable for afforestation but not for plantations (low productivity areas, deep slopes etc.).

Figure 5. Global deforestation and afforestation

HWP and BECCS carbon accounting

Harvested wood products (HWP) carbon accounting follows the IPCC production approach (PA), which is the most commonly used methodology to calculate HWP carbon storage (IPCC 2019). The initial HWP carbon pool is calculated by using the production and trade data of HWP from FAOSTAT database from 1961 to 2020 (FAOSTAT 2025a). Based on this method the global HWP pool was a sink of about 300 MtCO₂/yr in 2020, which is comparable to global HWP pool estimates by (Johnston and Radeloff 2019). The HWP carbon storage and sink are considerably smaller than to the forest carbon storage and sink, typically HWP carbon storage is about 5% of forest above ground carbon storage and HWP carbon sink about 10% of forest carbon sink (Zhao et al. 2022). There are two reasons for this. First, about 75% of tree biomass is lost for harvest and forest industry residues when woody biomass is moved away from forests and converted to HWP. Second, the lifetime HWP (0-100 years depending on the product) is typically shorter than the lifetime of trees (10-500 years depending on the management).

In addition to HWP carbon storage, we also calculate bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS) carbon storage. The difference between them is that a half-life HWP vary from 0 to 35 years while BECCS has an infinite half-life, i.e., HWP are temporary carbon storages while BECCS is a permanent carbon storage. The share of bioenergy with BECCS is provided by the MESSAGE model and increases from 5% in 2030 to 75% in 2100 (IIASA 2018). The BECCS carbon capture rate typically varies between 25-75% depending on the final energy carrier. We assume that

BECCS carbon capture rate is 63%, which is an average value estimated from the MESSAGE model outcome.

Substitution effects and substitution carbon storage

For the EU and Brazil scenarios developed in D7.3, substitution effects and substitution carbon storage have been added to the model.

Substitution refers to the use of wood-based products to replace fossil fuel-based products. Substitution is modelled by using constant displacement factors from (Leskinen et al. 2018) and calculated relative to the baseline scenario substitution. If substitution is higher than in the baseline, then it is called “additional substitution” and if substitution is lower than in the baseline then it is called “reverse substitution”(AFRY 2024). Additional substitution decreases the consumption of fossil fuel-based products and associated carbon emissions while reverse substitution has the opposite effect.

Substitution effect is made comparable to other carbon storages by aggregating annual substitutions as a cumulative substitution storage. Substitution storage is a carbon storage of fossil fuels, which remains unused due to increased consumption of wood-based products.

Circular bioeconomy

Circular bioeconomy scenarios have been developed in the context of D7.3, requiring additional model development.

The circular economy is modelled as: 1) an increase in the maximum recycled wood collection rate from 50% to 75%, 2) the addition of sawnwood re-use in the model as an alternative to recycling, and 3) an extension in the cascading use of woody-biomass by excluding sawdust, woodchips and recycled wood energy use.

The supply of recycled wood is based on the final consumption of mechanical forest industry products, which is used to estimate total recycled wood pool, and on recycled wood collection rates. The maximum recycled wood collection rate is assumed to be 50% based on (Leek 2010). For historical periods, country-level collection rates are based on FAOSTAT post-consume wood data (FAOSTAT 2025b). For future periods, country-level collection rates are allowed to increase to 50% (for scenarios without circular bioeconomy) or 75% (for scenarios with circular bioeconomy). Recycled wood collection and utilization is limited in many countries by inadequate waste management, legislation and missing infrastructure, which implies that a 75% collection rate would require changes in legislation as well as investments in waste management and suitable infrastructure.

Sawnwood re-use refers to the practices that allow sawnwood reutilization in the new purpose after its usual lifetime instead of recycling it to lower quality products such as fiberboard or bioenergy (Cristescu et al. 2020; Psilovikos 2023). Hence, sawnwood re-use reduces the demand for virgin sawlogs. According to our estimates the share of sawnwood re-use can increase up to 50% of raw material usage of global sawnwood consumption. Figure 7 shows the material usage

shares of global sawnwood consumption in the baseline and in the circular economy scenarios from 2000 to 2100.

Other natural land division to abandoned land and natural land

In GLOBIOM, other natural land is divided in two land-cover classes: 1) Abandoned land (AbdLnd), and 2) Natural land (NatLnd). AbdLnd is abandoned agricultural land, which typically has low biodiversity value and degraded carbon stock. NatLnd is old-growth natural vegetation land such as savannas, prairies and open forests (not classified as forests), which have high biodiversity value and carbon stock. AbdLnd is allowed to be converted to other land-use according to GLOBIOM usual land-use change constraints (land conversion costs + maximum available land) while NatLnd conversion to other land-use is limited by applying higher land conversion costs for NatLnd than for AbdLnd. Higher land conversion costs eliminate most of NatLnd conversion to other land uses.

Since no good map of historically abandoned lands is available, we let the model decide the level of available AbdLnd for each period. Based on this method, the AbdLnd area increase from zero in 2000 to 270 Mha in 2040, and then starts decreasing depending on the scenario (Figure 6). In general, AbdLnd decreases over time, because it is converted to plantations, forests or agricultural land. On the other hand, some agricultural land area is abandoned due to changes in demand and/or productivity, which increases AbdLnd area over time.

Figure 6. Global abandoned land (AbdLnd) development relative natural land (NatLnd) in the baseline scenario

Figure 7. Material usage shares of global sawnwood consumption in the baseline (BASE) and in the circular economy scenarios (CIR)

Adjustments to the model for Europe and Brazil

In D7.3, scenarios have been developed to explore the potential impact of the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 (EUBDS) and of different types of land restoration policies in Brazil on the forest sector, forest carbon balance and biodiversity, based on the interest of forest supply chain stakeholders collected during our dedicated workshop (see D7.2). Model adjustments were made to allow for a more comprehensive analysis of forest carbon balance in these scenarios. This includes the addition of plantation carbon uptake (PLA) and of substitution effects and substitution carbon storage (SUBST) as described above. Therefore, in these scenarios, forest carbon storage consists of FOREST, PLA, HWP, BECCS and SUBST storages.

The EUBDS is implemented in the model in the same way as in (Fulvio et al. 2025). As targeted by the EUBDS, the EU27 protected forest area is increased from the current level i.e., 24% in 2020 to 30% in 2030. The 30% protection target is applied separately in each country and divided into 10% strict protection and 20% “closer-to-nature” protection (Fulvio et al. 2025). In addition, all primary forests are strictly protected, based on the Sabatini map (Sabatini et al. 2020).

Restoration in Brazil is modelled as periodic restoration and deforestation area constraints for the period 2030-2100. Periodic areas are based on the G4M model RPC1p9 afforestation and deforestation areas. Three different types of restoration policies are considered: 1) Restoration of degraded agricultural land and abandoned land to natural forests, which are managed for carbon storage and biodiversity, 2) Restoration to plantations, which are managed for roundwood production, and 3) Restoration to multifunctional plantations, which are managed for roundwood production as well as for carbon storage and biodiversity. In addition, a counterfactual, no restoration policy scenario is also considered, based on the G4M model RCPref afforestation and deforestation areas.

Wood-based products trade and regional competitiveness

The GLOBIOM model includes 22 traded wood-based products, which differ in units and level of value-addition (i.e., primary, semifinished, final). It is important to mention that energy crops are not included in the traded products in the model. The reason is that energy crops are low value-add products, which are usually not transported long distances or traded between the countries.

For simplicity, we do not consider here individual wood-based products bilateral trade flows, but only total net exports (i.e. difference between export volume and import volume aggregated over all products). The volume of total net exports reflects regional woody biomass resources, production costs and forest industry development state, and can be used as an indicator of regional economic competitiveness.

Aggregation over different wood-based products requires that they are converted in comparable units. There are different methods to convert wood-based products to comparable units (Lauri et al. 2021). Here we use here so called roundwood equivalent (RWeq) units, which measure wood-based products according to the amount of primary biomass needed for their production. This method is standard in the forest sector analysis and has also been recently applied in the agricultural sector analysis (Zhao et al. 2025).

Aquaculture and aquafeed supply chains

Improving projections of unfed aquaculture capacity beyond 2020

As compared to the description of the BAU scenario in D6.2, and in accordance with the feedback received from stakeholders during the workshop, we assumed the capacity of unfed aquaculture systems to increase beyond 2020 levels in the future. To parameterize the post-2020 developments capacity of unfed aquaculture, we extrapolated historical trends at country- and product-levels using a Generalized Additive Models. Resulting future trends in capacity are presented in Figure 8. These trends are used for all scenarios in D7.2 and D7.3, except for the UNFED20 scenario.

Figure 8 - Projections for the capacity of unfed aquaculture by region and product

Parameterizing a scenario for changes in aquafeed crop composition

For all aquafeed and aquaculture scenarios presented in D7.2 and D7.3, except for the AFKOMPOCROP MIX scenario, we assumed the proportion of various crops (between soya, corn, rape and wheat) in total crop aquafeed demand to be country-specific (based on Frohlich, Halley, Runge et al 2018), but invariant across time horizons and scenarios.

As this might not necessarily be a valid assumption, and might affect the potential impact of crop aquafeed requirements on land use and biodiversity, we tested the impact of an alternative assumption in a simple scenario. In this alternative scenario (AFKOMPOCROP MIX), we focused on the dominant fed aquaculture production system (i.e., fed aquaculture in China), for which we assumed that 50% of the crude protein content from corn (which has relatively lower crude protein content) and soya (which is imported) feed requirements per unit of aquaculture output are replaced by a similar crude protein content from wheat. To do so, parameters for corn and soya aquafeed requirements were halved, while that of wheat was increased by the amount

necessary to compensate this loss in terms of crude protein intake (while accounting for differences across crops in crude protein content and apparent digestibility, see Table 3).

Table 3 - Nutritional parameters of individual crops as aquafeed

CROP	Crude protein content (gram crude protein per gram of freshmatter)	Apparent digestibility (fraction)
Corn	0.216	0.92
Soya	0.404	0.912
Wheat	0.404	0.95

Source: (INRAE/CIRAD/AFZ 2024)

Parameterizing a scenario for sustainable fisheries management

As discussed in D6.3 and D7.2, sustainable fisheries management is an important sustainability consideration for the blue food sector, regularly mentioned in the literature and mentioned as well by the stakeholders during the workshop.

About a third of fishery stocks are overfished (Sharma et al. 2025): in those stocks the current fisheries management is driving fish population decline that can ultimately lead to ecosystem disruptions, species extinction and food insecurity (through declining catch levels). Effective fisheries management can allow for the long-term maintenance and recovery of fish stocks, with a positive impact on catch potentials over a few years for overfished stocks, despite an initial reduction in catch levels. Globally, a wider adoption of sustainable fisheries management is expected to increase the level of catch while reducing overall risks to ocean ecosystems. For example, as illustrated in Figure 9, (Elleby et al. 2025) estimated that keeping current fisheries management would lead to a gradual decline in catch levels globally. On the other hand, they estimated that harvesting all fish stocks to a level of catch equivalent to the fish mortality rate that produces the Maximum Sustainable Yield (MSY) would lead to an initial drop in catches globally, but would break even globally with the current management scenario within less than a decade for overfished stocks. It would also lead to a net gain globally for all stocks as compared to the current catch level, with gains of about 15% for the first decades, and converging to gains of about 22% over a century or so. The authors found such a scenario to reduce the need for aquaculture growth, and have knock-on effects on the agricultural sector.

Figure 9 - Illustration of impact of alternative fishery management on catch levels globally (reproduced from (Elleby et al. 2025)). The figure provides trajectories of the level of catch from 2020 onwards (projection year) over short (left panels) and long (right panels) time horizons, for overfished (upper panels) and all fish stocks (lower panels), under two scenarios (current management $F_{current}$ in red, F_{MSY} management in light blue).

While we were not able to gather detailed data on fish species- and region-specific trajectories for catches under such scenarios, we used the aggregated findings from (Elleby et al. 2025) to parameterize a sustainable fisheries transition scenario. We therefore assumed that under such a scenario, the potential catch level would increase by 15% after 2020, for all species and regions. This assumption was implemented in scenario SUSFISH in D7.3.

Parameterizing a scenario for more sustainable blue food diets

As pointed out in the literature and by stakeholders during our workshop, another important sustainability lever lies with consumers. With agriculture and blue food products varying in their nutritional and environmental impacts, consumption choices can play an important role in shaping human health- and environmental degradation-related outcomes, including among aquaculture products (Gephart and Golden 2022).

While a detailed exploration of alternative and context-specific dietary preferences on multiple sustainability dimensions is out of scope, we designed a simple scenario to test the influence of such criteria. We assume a gradual substitution between freshwater species (the most growing species group in our baseline) and mollusks (a species group consistently well on both nutritional and environmental outcomes in (Gephart and Golden 2022)) between 2020 and 2050, in regions where consumption of freshwater species is high (most of SEA, SAS and EAS regions, except for Japan and South Korea). As a result, by 2050, 20% of the calories consumed as freshwater species in our baseline scenario are replaced in these regions by calories from mollusks species. This assumption is featured in scenario BFDIET in D7.3.

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